

THE PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO
THE STUDY OF THE TRIAD N-C-S. PART IX.
THIOBENZAMIDE.

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In continuation of the previous work on phenylthiocarbamides the decompositions of thiobenzamide have been studied (i) with hydrolytic agents (ii) with nitrous acid under various conditions of p_H . The reaction with nitrous acid in the presence of weak acid shows that thiobenzamide is 40% in the form of $C_6H_5CSNH_2$ in neutral solution; other decompositions are simple and show that this configuration is almost completely changed by acids and alkalis to the isothioamide form C_6H_5CSHNH .

The chemistry of phenylthiocarbamides has been investigated in these laboratories with a view to study their structure in solution under different conditions of p_H (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 627, 635, 639; 1937, 14, 474, 478; 1938, 15, 217, 221). The problem was attacked chiefly through two reactions viz. (i) the action of hydrolytic agents and (ii) the action of nitrous acid on these compounds. The decomposition varied according to the p_H of the solution. As in these cases the decompositions were complicated by the presence of two apparently similar nitrogen atoms, a simpler case of triad N-C-S in thiobenzamide has been studied in the present investigation.

In the presence of normal alkali thiobenzamide decomposes chiefly into benzonitrile and hydrogen sulphide (67%) according to the equation

Traces of ammonia are also produced but this is due to a secondary decomposition (*vide experimental*).

With normal acid, benzoic acid, hydrogen sulphide and ammonia are produced thus

and this occurs to the extent of 10%. The change also occurs to some extent (2%) even in neutral solution.

The action of nitrous acid on thiobenzamide has also been studied in the presence of strong acid and using one equivalent of sodium nitrite, the gas phase is mostly nitric oxide (79%), a change typical of the thio-carbamides; the oxidation product is a neutral product (m.p. 90°) which

proves to be dibenzylazosulphime (*Ber.*, 1892, 26, 1578), obtained by Gabriel and Hofmann by the interaction of alcoholic solution of iodine and thiobenzamide. Unchanged thiobenzamide still remains and if two molecular equivalents of nitrous acid are employed, the amount of the gas evolved is almost double with the same composition as above. The gas phase and the identity of the oxidation product show the change to be

In the presence of weak acid using one equivalent of sodium nitrite the gas phase is N (40%) and NO (60%); but there is evidence to show that the reaction giving nitrogen occurs first

Dibenzylsulphime is still formed but to a less extent.

The action of sodium nitrite in the presence of weak acid suggests that thiobenzamide is present in neutral solution only to the extent of 40% in the configuration $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CSNH}_2$, since the presence of a weak acid is not likely to disturb the configuration of the compound. This is supported by the hydrolytic decomposition. Acids and alkalis completely change the configuration to the form

which easily suffers desulphurisation and is easily oxidised.

Now it has been also found that the decrease in sulphide, observed in case of phenylthiocarbamide (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 641) but not explained by the authors, is to be attributed to the oxidation of sulphide to thiosulphate and sulphite, in presence of air. It has been found that the percentage composition studied in the presence of hydrogen remains the same. Thus the decrease noted in the case of thiobenzamide may also be attributed to the same cause.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Hydrolytic Reactions.

Expt. 1. Decomposition of Thiobenzamide by Boiling with Aqueous Caustic Potash.—Thiobenzamide (6.85 g.) and one equivalent of normal

caustic potash (50 c.c.) were refluxed together for 1 hour in a 500 c.c. round-bottomed flask, traces of ammonia being evolved. The contents of the flask were cooled and then distilled in steam for 10 minutes. The distillate contained an oil (b.p. 191°) identified as benzonitrile by hydrolysis with 70% sulphuric acid to benzoic acid and ammonia. The residual alkaline liquor contained much sulphide and some unchanged thiobenzamide. In a similar experiment omitting steam distillation sulphide was estimated by titrating against standard ammoniacal zinc solution. (Found: H_2S , 67 per cent). Ammonia was found to be 3%, estimated by absorbing in Volhard's trap containing excess of standard acid. It was found that alkali sulphide slowly decreased if boiling was continued for a longer period. Now it has been also found that the decrease in sulphide, previously studied in case of phenylthiocarbamide but not then explained, is attributed to the oxidation of sulphide to thiosulphate and sulphite, in the presence of air. It has been found that the percentage of sulphide in four and eight hours remains 21% in the presence of hydrogen. Oxidation is excluded if the experiment is conducted throughout the period of boiling in presence of hydrogen (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 641).

Expt. 2. Action of Cold Concentrated Alkali on Thiobenzamide.—Thiobenzamide (1 g.) and potassium hydroxide (3.66 g.) were added to water (7 c.c.), a solution resulting in the cold, an emulsion of benzonitrile being produced immediately but no ammonia; therefore ammonia formed in the last experiment is to be attributed to the secondary changes.

Expt. 3. Decomposition of Thiobenzamide by Boiling with Aqueous Hydrochloric Acid.—Thiobenzamide (6.85 g.) and one equivalent of normal hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) were refluxed together for 1 hour. Hydrogen sulphide formed was absorbed in Volhard's trap containing normal caustic potash (15 c.c.) and sulphide was estimated by titrating against ammoniacal zinc solution as before. (Found: H_2S , 9.5 per cent) and ammonia (10%) (found by difference in the titre value of the acid before and after the hydrolysis). No benzonitrile could be detected in this case.

Expt. 4. Decomposition of Thiobenzamide by Boiling with Water.—Thiobenzamide (6.85 g.) and water (50 c.c.) were boiled for 1 hour under reflux condenser attached to a trap containing 3% basic lead acetate (15 c.c.). (Found: PbS , 0.2468 i.e., H_2S , 2 per cent). The hydrolysed product contained benzoic acid and unchanged thiobenzamide. The reaction went in an analogous manner to that of acidic hydrolysis.

Action of Nitrous Acid on Thiobenzamide in the presence of a Strong Acid.

Expt. 5. In Molecular Proportion of 1 : 1 (gas phase).—Thiobenzamide

(0.0685 g.; $\frac{1}{2}$ mg. molecule) was tapped into the cup of Lunge's nitrometer. Sodium nitrite (0.5 c.c., $\frac{1}{2}$ mg. molecular proportion) was added and the reaction started by the addition of 1 c.c. of 4 N-HCl. Gas evolved was 10.8 c.c. at 24° and 748 mm *i.e.*, 9.4 c.c. at N.T.P. After the treatment with FeSO₄ volume was 2. c.c. at N.T.P. The composition was therefore NO, 77.8; N, 22.2 per cent.

*Expt. 6. In Molecular Proportion of 2 : 1 in two stages (gas phase).—*Expt. 1 was repeated and the evolved gas expelled from the nitrometer. Sodium nitrite (0.5 c.c. $\frac{1}{2}$ mg., second molecular proportion) was added. The evolution of the gas was slower than with the first equivalent. Gas evolved was 8.5 c.c. at 21.5° and 748 mm. or 7.6 c.c. at N.T.P. (Found: N, 25.3; NO, 74.7 per cent).

*Expt. 7. In Molecular Proportion of 2 : 1 in one stage (gas phase).—*Expt. 6 was repeated except that sodium nitrite (1 c.c., 1 mg. molecular proportion) was added in one stage. Gas evolved was 19.5 c.c. at 23.5° and 747 mm. or 17.14 c.c. at N.T.P. (Found: N, 24.6; NO, 75.4 per cent).

*Expt. 8. Action of Nitrous acid on Thiobenzamide (neglecting the gas phase).—*Thiobenzamide (137 g., 1 mg. molecular proportion) was dissolved in 40 c.c. of dilute alcohol (1:1) and mixed with 4 N-HCl (20 c.c.), and when crystals just appeared the solution was treated drop by drop with sodium nitrite (10 c.c.). The reaction occurred with effervescence and evolution of nitric oxide. A pink solid was formed and the mother-liquor when treated with alkaline lead acetate gave a precipitate of lead sulphide showing that unchanged thiobenzamide was still present. The pink solid was extracted with hot alcohol and filtered from the resinous mass and the filtrate deposited silky needles (m.p. 90°), identical with dibenzylazosulphime (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 1578). (Found: N, 11.8; S, 13.4. Calc. for dibenzylazosulphime, C₁₄H₁₀N₂S: N, 11.8; S, 13.4 per cent). Mixed melting point with Hofmann's compound, prepared by the interaction of alcoholic solution of iodine and thiobenzamide, was also 90°. If two molecular proportions of sodium nitrite were used the amount of dibenzylazosulphime formed was larger and very little unchanged thiobenzamide was left in the solution after the experiment.

Action of Nitrous Acid on Thiobenzamide in the presence of a Weak Acid.

*Expt. 9. In Molecular Proportion 1 : 1 (gas phase).—*The rest of the procedure was the same except that here 2N-acetic acid (1 c.c.) was added after the addition of sodium nitrite so that the configuration of thiobenzamide might not be disturbed and the reaction might start in the

least pH at the very outset. The action began with effervescence but not so vigorously as was noted in the case of hydrochloric acid. Gas evolved was 8.5 c.c. at 21.5° and 747 mm. or 7.6 c.c. at N.T.P. (Found: N, 38.1; NO, 61.9 per cent). If in the experiment the evolved gas was examined after 5 minutes of the start of the reaction the composition was found to be N, 50%; NO, 50% showing thereby that the normal reaction of nitrous acid on an amino group occurred first.

Expt. 10. In Molecular Proportion 1:1 (neglecting the gas phase).— Thiobenzamide (1.37 g.) was treated with sodium nitrite (10 c.c.) and 2*N*-acetic (20 c.c.) as was done in case of hydrochloric acid. The reaction was slow and nitric oxide was evolved. Some pink solid was formed and floated on the solution. The pink solid was proved to be dibenzylazosulphine as in the case of hydrochloric acid.

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